

Case Report

Two-Year Study of a Case of Medication-Related Osteonecrosis of the Lower Jaw Treated With Platelet-Rich Fibrin

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Abstract

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Osteonecrosis of the jaw (MRONJ) is associated with the consequences of taking antiresorptive or antiangiogenic medicine for bone metastases or osteoporosis. MRONJ is characterized by open necrotic bone in the maxillofacial area that lasts more than eight weeks. The management of such a condition depends on several factors, among which the choice of MRONJ therapeutic method is considered to be the leading one. However, to date, no specific treatment with a uniform standard of treatment has been established. The purpose of this article is to present the outcome of surgical treatment of MRONJ with the addition of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF). A case of a woman with Medication-related osteonecrosis of the lower jaw, whose condition was monitored for a period of two years, is presented.

Keywords: Innovative method, Lower jaw, PRF, MRONJ, Osteonecrosis, Open necrotic bone

INTRODUCTION

There is currently no specific standard treatment for cases of MRONJ. Usually, the first choice of treatment is by applying a conservative approach, which includes local removal of bone sequestration and the association of systemic antibiotic treatment or antiseptic solutions. Most cases can lead to a reduction in clinical signs and symptoms or to a complete cure. To improve the predictability of surgical treatment and healing, some therapeutic protocols have been proposed in recent years, such as low-level laser therapy (Scoletta et al., 2010), hyperbaric oxygen (Ripamonti et al., 2011), ozone therapy, (Freiberger et al., 2012) and autologous platelet concentrates (Adornato et al., 2007). One of the modern methods is related to the surgical treatment with the use of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) (Adornato et al., 2007). This alternative approach aims to add growth factors to the surgical site to accelerate the healing of bones and soft tissues.

The purpose of this article is to describe the outcome of surgical treatment of MRONJ using PRF in a female

patient diagnosed with medication-related osteonecrosis of the lower jaw.

CASE REPORT

It concerns a female patient who is admitted for treatment at the Clinic of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery in the city of Plovdiv, who has been diagnosed with medication-related osteonecrosis of the lower jaw. The patient was repeatedly treated by various specialists, such as dentists and oral surgeons, with the application of medicine therapy, which included osteotropic antibiotics and by smoothing the exposed bony edges of the oral jaw. After resection was offered, the patient abandoned a further conservative approach and sought help from our team. The patient, meanwhile, has been receiving intravenous monthly Zommeta for 5 years. The initial carcinoma with which the patient was diagnosed was on the breast and after the detection of bone metastases, she underwent

Figure 1. Local area before treatment

Figure 2. PRF

Figure 3. 2 years after treatment with PRF

intravenous therapy with this preparation. Osteonecrosis was established after extraction of a tooth on the lower jaw on the left, and in the previous dental treatment, the necessary measures were not taken to prevent medication-related osteonecrosis of the jaw. The patient was treated using platelet-rich fibrin. Under local

anesthesia, the mucoperiosteal flap was dissected, the necrotic portion of the mandible existed, and PRF was applied, then sutured tightly. The patient's condition was monitored for 2 years, with follow-up examinations every 3 months. The results of the treatment are satisfactory. Figure 1,2 and 3

DISCUSSION

In 2017, Maluf, G. et al reported two cases involving women with breast cancer who were treated with zoledronic acid and showed advanced MRONJ. Both cases were treated with surgical resection of the necrotic bone, followed by placement of an LPRF membrane. A complete healing of the wounds and intact mucosal coating was achieved (Maluf et al., 2017).

In 2017, Raeissadat, S.A. et al. make a comparison between PRGF and PRF in vitro (Ruggiero et al., 2009). PRGF shows a higher stimulatory role in the survival and proliferation of human gingival fibroblasts and is considered a means of periodontal regeneration.

Platelet-rich preparations have antimicrobial properties and can therefore be a beneficial natural tool for controlling postoperative infections at the site of surgery. The specific mechanisms of action in the interaction with microbial pathogens deserve further in-depth study.

The clinical use of PRF for regenerative therapy has also shown that the biological outcomes of periodontal and endodontic therapy can be improved if it acts primarily as an analogous extracellular matrix (Pradeep et al., 2012).

One of the strengths of this clinical report is the relatively long follow-up period, which is greater than 24 months. During the follow-up, the patient had no complications and the healing of the soft and hard tissues was maintained over time.

CONCLUSION

Long-term follow-up of the patient's condition in the postoperative period of PRF treatment proved the high percentage (91.6%) of successful cases of satisfactorily cured found in a number of literature sources (Del Fabbro et al., 2012; De Andrade et al., 2018; De Almeida Barros et al., 2018; Del Fabbro et al., 2011). The presented case with the use of PRF in the treatment medication-related osteonecrosis gives excellent results. During the two-year postoperative follow-up period, the typical severe pain, frequent abscesses, skin and mucosal fistulas were not found. Also, as a positive factor, we believe that jaw resection is not necessary. The use of platelet-rich fibrin (PRF) is an innovative method and gives good results. The therapeutic protocol can be used to treat MRONJ diseases without the need for jaw resections. It is also essential not to overlook the importance of informing the patient of the possibilities for this type of treatment, and to refer to a specialist surgeon to perform it.

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